

**PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF TEACHING STAFF - WAYS TO
SOLVE THE PROBLEM OF IMPROVING THE LEVEL OF TRAINING
OF CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL INSTITUTIONS OF THE REPUBLIC
OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. This article examines the problem of developing the professional readiness of preschool education teachers in Uzbekistan, with special attention paid to key aspects related to the development of personnel in the country's preschool education sector.

Key words: preschool education, quality of education, professional training of personnel, preschool institutions, improving the level, children.

Currently, Uzbekistan faces an acute problem of providing preschool institutions with professional teaching staff capable of solving educational and training tasks. The complexity of solving this problem is due to the following factors.

On the one hand, the attitude of parents and the public to the preschool period of childhood, to raising a child in a kindergarten, has changed.

In the first years of independence, new types of preschool educational institutions began to open in Uzbekistan: "Khonadon bogchasi" ("Home kindergarten"), "Maktab bogchasi" ("School kindergarten") [2]. Much attention was paid to the development of personal qualities of educators. However, if we critically assess the activities of preschool educational institutions in the first twenty-five years of independence, we can see that they were far from the level of modern requirements both in quantitative and qualitative terms.

Therefore, the latest government decrees have currently defined the status of a preschool educational institution, which has become the first step in the general educational structure, as a result of which the kindergarten is obliged to provide parents with the right to choose educational services and priorities in raising their child.

"We must provide a decent education to our young generation, stimulate their interest in science and knowledge. It is necessary," the head of state emphasized, "to develop the preschool education system, strengthen the material and technical base of secondary and higher education institutions, and radically improve the quality of scientific and educational processes" [1].

The high level of parental requirements for preschool education is a consequence of their awareness of the importance of the preschool childhood period, during which the physical and mental qualities of the individual, necessary for a person throughout his or her subsequent life, are intensively formed. Therefore, great responsibility lies with preschool teachers, who are called upon by the role of their activities to promote the development of the child's personality, creating optimal conditions for his mental and physical health. And only highly qualified teaching staff can implement these functions. But, on the other hand, low wages, high psycho-emotional load with irregular work, huge responsibility for the life and safety of children, the "lack of prestige" of the profession in the eyes of young people - these are objective social and economic reasons contributing to the mass outflow of young teaching staff from preschool institutions.

There is an alternative for parents to state preschool institutions - a network of private kindergartens both in the city of Tashkent and throughout the Republic, but fees in the private sector of preschool institutions are sky-high, the monthly fee for one child is from 4,000,000 to 10,000,000 sums. With an average salary of citizens of Uzbekistan of 3,000,000 sums, visiting such kindergartens is almost impossible.

Training of specialists - educators in these private kindergartens is carried out in advanced training institutes of the city of Tashkent, programs, methods, and notes are used in private kindergartens in Russia, control and monitoring of their training of young citizens of the Republic is not carried out.

Teachers-educators of state preschool institutions also improve their qualifications in advanced training institutes, where they receive the necessary amount of knowledge, skills and abilities to work in their preschool institutions. Increased demands on the teacher-educator working with a small child in state preschool institutions from parents, education authorities (MNO, GUNO, OBOLONO) and the public, and low material and moral assessment of their work are the objective factors that make the task of providing preschool institutions with pedagogical factors difficult to accomplish.

The main teaching contingent of preschool institutions is women aged 35 to 65 years. Today, almost every preschool institution in the Tashkent district has enough teachers-educators, the staff is fully staffed.

In conversations with young educators who have special pedagogical education and have recently started working, there is another subjective factor - the lack of high-quality special professional knowledge in the field of psychological and pedagogical disciplines does not allow young personnel to feel comfortable and confident at work. The objective difficulties they encounter in the process of working with preschool children are aggravated by the lack of knowledge, skills and abilities in pedagogical activity, which negatively affects the development of a positive attitude towards the activity and the formation of sustainable professional interest, and therefore does not contribute to the creative self-realization of the individual.

In the city and regional institutes for advanced training, the preschool education department has organized courses for preschool specialists who do not have a special preschool education, which are very popular with preschool teachers, and at Pedagogical College No. 2, a correspondence department has been operating for several years, where teachers working in preschool institutions in the city of Tashkent receive an education (however, in Russian groups, two teachers teach subjects, with an average of 10 subjects each, which reduces the quality of obtaining special pedagogical knowledge for students studying in Russian groups). Last year, a new program "Ilk qadam" was released for preschool institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which was distributed free of charge to all preschool institutions of the republic in the state language (there is no translation into Russian, which reduces the quality of education in Russian-speaking groups), this year, training courses were held in all regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the regional institute for advanced training of preschool workers, the authors of this program. [3]. At which specialists of preschool institutions had the opportunity to meet with the authors of the program "Ilk qadam" to ask them questions and receive qualified answers on the new program.

Currently, the authors of the program "Ilk qadam" are developing methodological guidelines, educational and didactic materials, lesson plans, visual and illustrative materials for all age groups, which will help teachers of preschool institutions to professionally and efficiently teach and educate preschool children in kindergartens.

The participants of the meetings noted the importance of these teaching and methodological developments of the authors for the program "Ilk qadam", since they

were absent from the previous programs "Bolajon", "Child of the Third Millennium", especially the participants of the seminars asked for such materials as notes, illustrative material on the decorative and applied arts of Uzbekistan on the methodology of fine art, since they noted that much had been missed over 17 years, in the previous program this significant section was missing from the program.

.... We believe that the methodological basis for the high-quality training of preschool specialists should be an "activist" concept, according to which the learning process depends on the activity of educators, on the level of development of their independence in cognitive activity. This presupposes a significant expansion of the traditional sector of pedagogical influence, the basis of which is a subjective approach to the student, providing for a shift in emphasis from reproductive methods of perception to stimulating independence and creative initiative, the formation and development of professional thinking and self-knowledge. In the process of theoretical and practical training, future educators must acquire basic professional and pedagogical skills, namely:

***design and prognostic:** the ability to set goals and formulate tasks of pedagogical activity, the ability to plan and draw up a plan for working with children, the ability to predict the development and education of a child's personality, the results of certain pedagogical influences.

***organizational:** the ability to organize different types of activities with children and adults;

***methodological:** mastery of techniques for working with children, the ability to implement an individual approach, develop creative abilities;

***diagnostic:** the ability to study the personality of a child, the conditions and equipment of the pedagogical process, pedagogical documentation, the ability to analyze the activities of children, teachers, parents; develop a test, a diagnostic card, determine the level of development of the child, draw up a psychological and pedagogical characteristic;

***communicative:** the ability to purposefully organize and manage communication, speak publicly in front of a group of teachers, parents; resolve conflict situations, manage your behavior and mood, clearly and convincingly express your thoughts.;

***research:** knowledge of research methods, ability to study and generalize advanced pedagogical experience;

***applied:** ability to produce didactic materials, toys, aesthetically and pedagogically competently design exhibitions, stands, etc.

It is necessary that the educators of our preschool institutions be able to fit into the innovative regime of modern preschool institutions of Uzbekistan, be oriented towards creativity, pedagogical improvisation, search for new methods, techniques and forms of education and training, be ready for experimental and search work.

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